

**IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LANGUAGE TEACHING AND IMPLEMENTING
MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN.****Hilola Sayfiddinovna Turakulova****Lecturer in the Department of Foreign Languages****“Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage****Samarkand, Uzbekistan****+998882706266****hilola6266@gmail.com****khilolaturakulova@univ-silkroad.uz****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10154590>**

Abstract: The role of foreign language is huge. We know that over the years, English has become the most popular and widely spoken language in the world. It is the main language of business, sports, science. In our country, special attention is paid to learning and using three languages: Uzbek, Russian and English. The idea of the trinity of languages is especially important for Uzbekistan.

Key words: Pedagogical technology, Educational technology, Project method, Modular teaching, Communicative education, Problem-based teaching technology, Information communication technologies, Game technologies of foreign language teaching.

In the pedagogy inevitably arise questions such as: «How to teach English?» «What to teach?», «Why to teach?» but, however, there is another one: «How to teach productively?». In my opinion, one of the options decision these questions – it is to use of modern pedagogical technologies in educational process.

As said Johann Wolfgang von Goethe.

«Thinking is easy, acting is difficult, and to put one's thought into action is the most difficult thing in the world».

The word "technology" comes from the Greek words "techno" - art, skill and "logos" - science, law. Literally, technology is the science of skill.

What is pedagogical technology? In pedagogy, the term "technology" began to be used in the 60s of the 20th century as a systematic method of studying the actions of students and teachers.

The introduction of "technology" into pedagogy and methodology is related to the teachers' desire to control the educational process. At the same time, the technological approach to the construction of the educational process is developing. An attempt to create a holistic methodology of teaching and learning process management by students is reflected in programmed education. In the 70s of the last century, in the USA, and then in Western Europe, programmed teaching was considered as a pedagogical method and the foundation of educational technologies was built. In foreign sciences, the term "technology" is associated with the term "education". Later, the terms "pedagogical technology" and "educational technology" appeared in pedagogical literature.

Pedagogical technology is a field of research and practice related to all aspects of the organization of pedagogical systems and the way resources are allocated to achieve specific and potentially repeatable pedagogical results.

Teachers use both traditional and new forms and methods of teaching in their activities in order to achieve positive results in educating and educating future schoolchildren; as well as using the author's technology, own developments.

This topic is not sufficiently developed and, in fact, because currently an active process of informatization of education is underway, which includes the rapid introduction and use of new pedagogical technologies, the use of all means of communication. An intellectually developed creative person who is well oriented in the information space, ready for self-development and the use of this knowledge in his future professional activities.

Currently, the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process is very relevant. It helps to activate the cognitive activity of students, stimulates and develops cognitive processes: thinking, perception, memory. The use of pedagogical technologies in English classes allows students to acquire grammatical skills in a bright, interesting way, to correct the material in an interesting way using technologies that help to correctly perceive the material on this or that topic.

I analyzed various definitions of the concepts of "educational technology" and "educational technology" found in foreign pedagogical literature and the characteristics of this pedagogical phenomenon. Bruner J. considers it to be an area concerned with setting requirements that ensure the optimization of education. The definition of educational technology officially recognized by the American Association for Educational Communication and Technology in 1979 considers educational technology to be complex integrative. process, including people, ideas, methods and tools for organizing problem analysis activities, and management of problem solving that encompasses all aspects of learning¹.

Considering the various definitions, it should be noted that foreign researchers distinguish such essential features of educational technology as diagnostic goal formation, guaranteed productivity, efficiency, algorithmization, projectability, integrity, manageability, correction ability, visualization. Polish scientist and educator F. Yanushkevich focuses on the sign of the efficiency of technology. He notes that educational technology is «the guidance system, which should provide the training of an expert of the necessary profile for perhaps shorter deadlines at optimum expenses of forces and means during the use of modern methods and tutorials»².

The project method is one of the modern teaching methods in which children solve a practical problem for several days or weeks. This might include building a rocket, designing a playground, or publishing a class newspaper. Projects may be suggested by the teacher, but they are planned and carried out by the students themselves, individually or in groups whenever possible. The work of the project is aimed at increasing the activity and motivation of students in order to apply certain knowledge or skills, not to give them, but to use them, and to develop independent thinking, self-confidence and social responsibility³.

One of the achievements of the technique of teaching foreign languages is the theory of communicative teaching. The technology of the communicative teaching method developed on its basis provides communication-based teaching. Despite the fact that it was developed relatively long ago, it is still relevant and in demand. In addition, communication-based teaching is the essence of all intensive foreign language teaching methods. The use of speaking and thinking tasks is a key element of communicative learning. It ensures the implementation of all other

¹ Bruner J. The course of cognitive growth // American psychologist. – 2019.

² Yanushkevich F. Educational Technology in higher education. – M.: Higher school, 2016.

³ Brauer G. Pedagogy of Language Learning in Higher Education: An Introduction. – Ablex Publishing Corporation, 2021.

communicative features, such as learning motivation, activity, student-teacher interaction, meaningfulness, problem and situation orientation, functionality, emotionality⁴.

One of the most effective modern technologies for teaching foreign languages is problem-based learning technology. The use of this technology ensures the stimulation of the independent search activity of the student's mind, which consists of the difference between the existing knowledge and the knowledge required to solve the problem or problematic task set by the teacher. The main structural elements of problem-based learning are a problem situation and the process of solving it, a problem task and a problem question⁵.

However, now a new technology has become widespread - information and communication technologies (ICT) in foreign language teaching, developed on the basis of the above-mentioned technology. Traditional methods of storing, transmitting and processing information become ineffective. The use of ICT provides great opportunities for both teachers and students. Understanding ICT is mainly related to the development of promising didactic tools such as electronic multimedia (learning programs, electronic textbooks, interactive multimedia, etc.); electronic educational resources (libraries, databases, virtual communication and interaction, websites, portals, etc.); educational internet resources. ICT is one of the components of the information-educational environment of the university, which consists of electronic products of various activities: informational, communicative, creative, software, technological, etc.

The game is one of the oldest methods of human cognitive activity. The concept of play has changed in recent social and scientific practice, and now it is considered as a social, serious category with special didactic value. Didactic game is an integral element of active learning, especially when it comes to teaching foreign languages. For example, role-playing and business games are very effective in this area. In the process of such games, students gradually enter a state of natural communication in a foreign language and can solve a number of creative and practical problems, realize their personal potential and demonstrate their skills. The components of the educational game include the so-called game style approach, that is, introducing predetermined conditions into the educational situation, changing the emotional color of the situation, the behavior of students already accepted in the lesson. - to change the attitude to the norms of actions and, accordingly, to the educational information. Such an approach is introduced when it is necessary to revise the existing knowledge, that is, to look at the situation from different points of view⁶.

Conclusion

When working with new technologies and the changing role of the teacher, whose main task – to support and guide the development of the personality of students, their creative search. Relationships with pupils are built on the principles of collaboration and co-creation. In these circumstances, inevitable revision of existing today organizational forms of educational work: an increase in selfindividual and group work of students, a departure from the traditional lesson with

⁴ Daniel J.S. Mega-universities and knowledge media: technology strategies for higher education. – London: Kogan Page, 2016.

⁵ VanGundy A.B. Activities for Teaching Creativity and Problem Solving. – Canada: John Wiley & Sons Canada Ltd, 2020.

⁶ Gredler M.E. Games and simulations and their relationships to learning / In D. Jonassen (Ed.), Handbook of research for educational communications and technology. – Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 2022.

a predominance of explanatory and illustrative teaching method, the increase in practical and creative work of search and research character.

In conclusion, the use of pedagogical technology allows solving a number of problems, in particular:

- increases students' activity in class;
- increases the motivation to study certain grammatical topics;
- creating conditions for independent work;
- creates a comfortable environment for learning;
- enables personalization of education;
- forms intellectual skills and computer skills.

Recent years have increasingly raised the issue of the application of new pedagogical technologies in high school. It is not only new facilities but also new forms and methods of teaching, new approach to learning. The introduction of new technologies in the teaching process increases, in my opinion, the teacher's authority in the school community, as taught in modern, higher level. In addition, the growing self-confidence of teachers to develop their professional competence. Application of new technologies in the classroom of English is an effective factor for the development of students' motivation.

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